

Enhanced Plant Histone Proteomics via Trimethylacetic Derivatization, Arg-C Ultra Digestion, and Flow Sorting of Nuclei

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Note: Protocols 5 and 3S, which were evaluated in the study as the preferred methods for histone preparation from maize and other crops, are presented. Although they are presented in the exact step-by-step format as performed in the study, protein-level derivatization can also be omitted in the FACS-based procedure by using Arg-C Ultra cleavage followed by TMA labeling instead of TMA-trypsin-TMA.

Protocol 5: Isolation of histones from crude nuclei, their precipitation, digestion with Arg-C Ultra and TMA labeling of histone peptides

Protocol 3S: Nuclei isolated by FACS followed by TMA labeling in combination with trypsin digestion

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1. Isolation of histones from crude nuclei, their precipitation, digestion with Arg-C Ultra and TMA labeling of histone peptides

Day 1

1.1. Nuclei isolation (Percoll gradient) and histone extraction

Solutions:

All solutions should be pre-cooled.

Buffer 5×A

50mM NaCl, 50mM 2-(N-morpholino) ethanesulfonic acid (MES; pH 6.0), 25mM EDTA, 1.25M sucrose, 3% Triton X-100, 750μM spermidine. Could be stored for 5 months at 0–4 °C.

Buffer 1×A

Prepare fresh. Dilute 1 part of Buffer 5×A with 4 parts of water, and add 20mM dithiothreitol (DTT).

Buffer B

Prepare fresh. 2.4 g of Buffer 5×A, 18 g of Percoll, and 20mM DTT.

PTM inhibitors

0.1mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF), 45mM sodium butyrate (histone deacetylase inhibitor), Protease Inhibitor cocktail (Sigma-Aldrich, P9599; 10 μL/ml), Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail 2 (Sigma-Aldrich, P5726; 10 μL/ml).

Washing buffer (WB):

75mM NaCl, 10mM EDTA, 50mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0).

Lysis buffer:

80mM NaCl, 20mM EDTA, 1% Triton X-100.

Acetone/HCl

50mM HCl in acetone.

It is essential to keep the samples, solutions, and the equipment (centrifuges, falcon tubes, mortar and pestle, etc.) between 0–4 °C throughout the whole procedure to prevent protein degradation and minimize PTM changes.

1. Grind the plant material under liquid nitrogen into a powder, and transfer with a spatula into falcon tubes containing 10 mL of cold 1xA buffer with PTM inhibitors. Homogenize the sample to “soft ice” consistency.
2. Filter the homogenate through nylon mesh folded over four times in a pre-cooled glass funnel. Refill all tubes to the same volume with water.
3. Centrifuge for 12 min at $3900 \times g$ (4 °C). Discard supernatant, wash the pellet thoroughly with 5 mL 1xA and centrifuge (12 min, $3900 \times g$, 4 °C). This step should be repeated a minimum of two times, or until the supernatant isn't completely transparent and clear.
4. Resuspend the pellet in 2 mL buffer B and centrifuge (10 min, $3900 \times g$, 4 °C).

5. Collect the upper layer containing the nuclear fraction. Transfer it to a new tube and add WB to a final volume of 14 mL. Resuspend the nuclei and centrifuge (5 min, 3900 × *g*, 4 °C), discard the supernatant.
6. Transfer 1 ml into the 1.5mL tube, resuspend and centrifuge (5 min, 3900 × *g*, 4 °C). Discard the supernatant.
7. Resuspend the pelleted nuclei in 0.5 mL of WB and centrifuge (5 min, 3900 × *g*, 4 °C). Discard the supernatant.
8. Resuspend the pelleted nuclei in 200 μL cold lysis buffer, supplemented with PTM inhibitors. Incubate for 1 h on ice, and centrifuge (5 min, 10,000 × *g*, 4 °C). Discard the supernatant completely.
9. Resuspend the pelleted chromatin with 200 μL 50mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), and centrifuge (5 min, 10,000 × *g*, 4 °C). Discard the supernatant.
10. For histone extraction, resuspend the pelleted chromatin in 250 μL of ice-cold 0.2 M H₂SO₄, and incubate overnight on a rotator at 4 °C.

Day 2

11. Centrifuge the sample (8 min, 16,100 × *g*, 4 °C), and collect the supernatant containing histone proteins.
12. Precipitate samples with 250 μL of 50 % TCA in water for 30 minutes. Wash precipitate with 1 mL acetone/HCl. Repeat washing the protein pellet twice with 1 mL of acetone. Re-dissolve clean histone extract in 30 μL of deionized water.
13. Optional: Take an aliquot of 1 μL from each sample to a microplate for protein concentration measurement using a Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit. Dilute each aliquot to a final volume of 50 μL with deionized water, add 50 μL of WR reagent, and incubate for 2 h at 37°C. Measure protein concentration at 562 nm.
14. If required, histone extract can be stored at -20 °C for several weeks.

1.2. Enzymatic digestion (Arg-C Ultra)

15. Use the entire volume of histone extract for subsequent Arg-C Ultra digestion and TMA labeling. The volumes of all reagents and solutions used in the following steps are calculated based on a 30 μL sample volume.
16. Add 0.5M ammonium bicarbonate (pH 7.5) and 200mM DTT to the sample to achieve final concentrations of 50 mM and 10 mM, respectively. Mix thoroughly.
17. Add Arg-C Ultra enzyme to the sample, corresponding to an enzyme:substrate ratio of 1:100. Incubate at 37 °C for 90 minutes to allow enzymatic digestion. Repeat the digestion under the same conditions to improve overall digestion efficiency.

1.3. Chemical derivatization of Lysines and Peptide N-termini (Peptide level)

Chemical derivatization at the peptide level is applied to label ε-amino groups of unmodified and monomethyl-lysine residues, as well as newly generated N-termini of histone peptides to improve chromatographic retention and detection during LC-MS/MS.

18. Add 10 μL of 100 % ACN to each sample.
19. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper and adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide.

20. Prepare derivatization reagent by mixing trimethylacetic anhydride with ACN in the ratio 1:3 (v/v); i.e., mix 2.25 μ L of trimethylacetic anhydride and 6.75 μ L of ACN, vortex, and spin shortly down. Continue immediately without any interruption.
21. Add 2.25 μ L of the reagent to the histone peptides immediately, add 0.5 μ L of ammonium hydroxide, and vortex.
22. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper, adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide, and spin down.
23. Incubate in a microwave oven at 350 W twice for 1 minute, spin in between.
24. Repeat steps 19-23 for the second and third rounds of derivatization.
25. Dry the sample out in a vacuum concentrator overnight.
26. If required, the protocol may be interrupted at this stage. Alkylated peptides can be stored at 4°C for several weeks. Otherwise, continue with the purification step.

Day 3

1.4. Sample purification using AttractSPE® Tips C18 (Affinisep)

Solutions:

Binding solution (BS)

0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)

Elution solution 1 (ES1)

0.1% TFA in 50% acetonitrile (ACN)

Elution solution 2 (ES2)

0.1% TFA in 75% ACN.

27. The dried digested histone extract should be resuspended in 50 μ L of BS. Check the sample pH is below 4 with a pH indicator paper.
28. Rehydrate the SpinTip by loading 20 μ L of ES2, spin down for 1 min in a microfuge (1,000 $\times g$, RT).
29. For equilibration, load SpinTip with 20 μ L of BS, spin down for 1 min (1,000 $\times g$, RT). Repeat loading and spinning down twice.
30. Load 50 μ L of sample into the SpinTip, spin down (1 min, 600 $\times g$, RT). In order to minimize the loss of material, wash the sample tube with 20 μ L of BS and transfer the solution to the SpinTip. Spin down for 1 min (600 $\times g$, RT).
31. Wash the sorbent twice with 20 μ L of BS, spin down after each washing (1 min, 1,000 $\times g$, RT).
32. Replace the tube with the new one. Peptides should be eluted twice with 10 μ L of ES1 and twice with 20 μ L of ES2. Each elution step should be finished with a 1 min spin down (600 $\times g$, RT).

1.5. Sample preparation for LC-MS/MS

33. Transfer the sample to an LC vial. Wash the collection tube with 30 μ L of ACN, and add the solution to the LC vial.
34. Reduce the sample volume to 10 μ L in vacuum concentrator (~15 min).

35. Acidify the sample with 10% FA to a final concentration of 1%.

2. Nuclei isolated by FACS followed by TMA labeling in combination with trypsin digestion

Day 1

Solutions:

Tris buffer

0.303 g Tris base

0.931 g Na₂EDTA

1.461 g NaCl

250 µl Triton X-100 (0.1% [v/v] final)

Adjust volume to 200 ml with dH₂O. Adjust pH to 7.5 using 1 N HCl.

Formaldehyde fixative

Add 13.5 ml of 37% (v/v) formaldehyde stock solution (Merck) to 237.5 ml Tris buffer. Prepare just before use.

LB01 buffer

0.363 g Tris base

0.149 g Na₂EDTA

0.035 g spermine-4HCl

1.193 g KCl

0.234 g NaCl

200 µl Triton X-100

Adjust volume to 200 ml with dH₂O. Adjust final pH to 9 using 1 N HCl. Filter through a 0.22-µm filter to remove small particles. Add 220 µl 2-mercaptoethanol and mix well.

DAPI (4,6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole) stock solution, 0.1 mg/ml

0.2 M H₂SO₄

2.1 Nuclei isolation (FACS) and histone extraction

1. Collect the leaves from 16-day-old maize plants and cut them into 2cm-long pieces.
2. Fix the leaves in 2% formaldehyde in Tris buffer for 20 min at 4°C.
3. Wash the leaves 3 x 5 min in Tris buffer.
4. Transfer the leaves into the glass Petri dish and prepare the nuclei suspension. Chop the leaves in 1mL of LB01 lysis buffer with a sharp razor blade.
5. Filter the crude nuclei suspension through 20µm-nylon mesh, and add DAPI (2µg/mL).
6. Analyze the suspension using a flow cytometer FACSAria SORP (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA). Introduce the sample and let it stabilize at the flow rate of 1000 particles/sec.
7. Set a gating region on a dot plot of forward scatter (FSC) and DAPI peak/pulse height to exclude debris, nuclei, and large clumps.
8. Isolate 1,000,000 of G1 nuclei into 2mL Low bind DNA Eppendorf tubes.
9. Centrifuge the nuclei at 3,000 × g for 5 min at 4°C.
10. Remove the supernatant and add 50 µL of 0.2M H₂SO₄ to the pellet for lysis and histone extraction. Incubate samples overnight on a rotator at 4 °C.

Day 2

1. Centrifuge the sample (8 min, $16,100 \times g$, 4°C), and collect the supernatant containing histone proteins.
2. Optional: Take an aliquot of $3\ \mu\text{L}$ from each sample to a microplate for protein concentration measurement using a Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit. Dilute each aliquot to a final volume of $50\ \mu\text{L}$ with deionized water, add $50\ \mu\text{L}$ of WR reagent, and incubate for 2 h at 37°C . Measure protein concentration at 562 nm.
3. If required, histone extract can be stored at -80°C for several weeks.

2.2. Chemical derivatization of lysines (protein level)

Chemical derivatization at the protein level is applied to block ϵ -amino groups of unmodified and monomethyl-lysine residues, giving longer peptides with better chromatographic retention following trypsin digestion.

4. Take histone extract in $0.2\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and adjust the pH to 8 with ammonium hydroxide. Reduce the sample volume to $20\ \mu\text{L}$ in vacuum concentrator.
5. Prepare derivatization reagent by mixing trimethylacetic anhydride with ACN in the ratio 1:3 (v/v); i.e., mix $3\ \mu\text{L}$ of trimethylacetic anhydride and $9\ \mu\text{L}$ of ACN, vortex, and shortly spin down. Continue immediately without any interruption.
6. Add $3\ \mu\text{L}$ of the reagent to the histone extract immediately, add $1\ \mu\text{L}$ of ammonium hydroxide, and vortex.
7. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper, adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide, and spin down.
8. Incubate in thermomixer at RT for 5h, 1000 rpm.
9. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper and adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide.
10. Repeat steps 5-8 for the second round of derivatization.
11. Incubate in thermomixer at RT for 16h, 1000 rpm.

Day 3

12. Concentrate the sample in a vacuum concentrator to $3\text{-}5\ \mu\text{L}$, resuspend the concentrated sample in 50% ACN to a final volume of $12\ \mu\text{L}$.
13. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper and adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide.
14. Prepare derivatization reagent by mixing trimethylacetic anhydride with ACN in the ratio 1:3 (v/v); i.e., mix $3\ \mu\text{L}$ of trimethylacetic anhydride and $9\ \mu\text{L}$ of ACN, vortex, and spin shortly down. Continue immediately without any interruption.
15. Add $3\ \mu\text{L}$ of the reagent to the histone extract immediately, add $1\ \mu\text{L}$ of ammonium hydroxide, and vortex.
16. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper, adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide, and spin down.
17. Incubate in a microwave oven at 350 W twice for 1 minute, spin in between.
18. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper and adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide.
19. Repeat steps 14-17 for second and third rounds of derivatization.

20. Concentrate the sample in a vacuum concentrator to 3-5 μL .

2.3. Enzymatic digestion (trypsin)

21. Resuspend concentrated sample in 40 μL of 100mM ammonium bicarbonate (pH 7.5). Check the sample pH is about 8 with a pH indicator paper.
22. Add Solu-trypsin to the final enzyme:substrate ratio of 1:40. Incubate at 37 °C for 4 hours to allow enzymatic digestion.
23. Repeat the digestion under the same conditions to improve overall digestion efficiency. Incubate at 37 °C for 16 hours.

Day 4

2.4. Chemical derivatization of peptide N-termini (peptide level)

Post-digestion labelling of newly generated N-termini of histone peptides is applied to improve chromatographic retention and detection during LC-MS/MS.

24. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper and adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide.
25. Prepare derivatization reagent by mixing trimethylacetic anhydride with ACN in the ratio 1:3 (v/v); i.e., mix 3 μL of trimethylacetic anhydride and 9 μL of ACN, vortex, and spin shortly down. Continue immediately without any interruption.
26. Add 3 μL of the reagent to the histone extract immediately, add 1 μL of ammonium hydroxide, and vortex.
27. Check the sample pH with a pH indicator paper, adjust to 8 with ammonium hydroxide, and spin down.
28. Incubate in a microwave oven at 350 W twice for 1 minute, spin in between.
29. Repeat steps 24-28 for the second and third rounds of derivatization.
30. Concentrate the sample in a vacuum concentrator to 3-5 μL .
31. Dry the sample out in a vacuum concentrator overnight.
32. If required, the protocol may be interrupted at this stage. Alkylated peptides can be stored at 4°C for several weeks. Otherwise, continue with the purification step.

Day 5

2.5. Sample purification using AttractSPE® Tips C18 (Affiniseq)

Solutions:

Binding solution (BS)

0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)

Elution solution 1 (ES1)

0.1% TFA in 50% acetonitrile (ACN)

Elution solution 2 (ES2)

0.1% TFA in 75% ACN.

33. The dried digested histone extract should be resuspended in 50 μL of BS. Check the sample pH is below 4 with a pH indicator paper.
34. Rehydrate the SpinTip by loading 20 μL of ES2, spin down for 1 min in a microfuge ($1,000 \times g$, RT).
35. For equilibration, load SpinTip with 20 μL of BS, spin down for 1 min ($1,000 \times g$, RT). Repeat loading and spinning down twice.
36. Load 50 μL of sample into the SpinTip, spin down (1 min,
37. $\times g$, RT). In order to minimize the loss of material, wash the sample tube with 20 μL of BS and transfer the solution to the SpinTip. Spin down for 1 min ($600 \times g$, RT).
38. Wash the sorbent twice with 20 μL of BS, spin down after each washing (1 min, $1,000 \times g$, RT).
39. Replace the tube with the new one. Peptides should be eluted twice with 10 μL of ES1 and twice with 20 μL of ES2. Each elution step should be finished with a 1 min spin down ($600 \times g$, RT).

2.6. Sample preparation for LC-MS/MS

40. Transfer the sample to an LC vial. Wash the collection tube with 30 μL of ACN, and add the solution to the LC vial.
41. Reduce the sample volume to 10 μL in a vacuum concentrator (~15 min).
42. Acidify the sample with 10% FA to a final concentration of 1%.